

EELISA

European University

OVERVIEW OF EELISA INNOVATION TALKS (2)

Deliverable 7.7

Date: 31 May 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Technical references

Grant Agreement number:	101035811
Project Acronym:	EELISA InnoCORE
Project title:	EELISA INNOVation and COMmon REsearch strategy
Start date of the project:	1 June 2021
Duration of the project:	36 months

Deliverable No.:	7.7 Overview of EELISA innovation talks (2)
Work Package:	7
Task:	7.4 EELISA innovation talks
Lead beneficiary:	FAU
Due date of deliverable:	31 May 2024
Actual submission date:	31 May 2024
Dissemination level:	Public

Document history

Version	Date	WP Leader	Reviewed by:
0.1	20 May 2024	FAU	First draft by David Schkade (FAU) with the support of Amira Watfa (FAU)
0.2	22 May 2024	FAU	Second draft modified following input from EELISA InnoCORE partners
0.3	23 May 2024	FAU	First quality check by László Gergely Vigh (BME)
0.4	27 May 2024	FAU	Second quality check by EELISA Executive Director (Sofia Costa d'Aguiar) and EELISA InnoCORE quality assurance coordinator (Juan Manuel Muñoz)
1.0	31 May 2024	FAU	Final version by David Schkade (FAU)

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811.

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

This document is prepared within the work package WP7 – “Create the ‘embedding’ for EELISA-wide R & I structures (Optimize outreach)”, as deliverable D7.7 “Overview of EELISA innovation talks (2)” of the project EELISA INNOvation and COmmon REsearch strategy (hereinafter referred to as EELISA InnoCORE), co-funded by European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101035811.

This deliverable (D7.7) gives an overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (2) from December 2022 to May 2024 including conclusions from events held with the number of live attendees and an evaluation of media distribution (hit rates etc.). It is a follow-up deliverable to D7.6 “Overview of EELISA innovation talks (1)” submitted in November 2022, which explained the concept and the implementation of EELISA Innovation Talks and gave an overview of the first five EELISA Innovation Talks. D7.7 continues the overview of EELISA Innovation Talks that was started in D7.6 and presents the last 13 EELISA Innovation Talks that were organized during the second reporting period from December 2022 to May 2024.

EELISA Innovation Talks were first conceptualized in task 7.4 and further elaborated in D7.6 with the aim to bring the knowledge generated in EELISA to the broader public while making EELISA a vibrant forum for innovation and Europe, and the world, a better place. These were the main goals of this monthly event series that gave the stage to our best EELISA researchers and innovators to discuss the possibilities, risks, and opportunities of technology and innovation for sustainable development. Each session was hosted by a different EELISA institution and streamed to the world on the EELISA YouTube channel from Madrid, Paris, Pisa, Erlangen, Nuremberg, Budapest, Bucharest, or Istanbul. Each partner institution could choose from a variety of appealing formats such as panel discussions, live talks, live interviews, or any other interactive format. In the first reporting period, the EELISA Innovation Talks were hosted by BME, FAU, UPB, SNS, and SSSA and in the second reporting period, the EELISA Innovation Talks were hosted by UPM, ITU, ENPC, UPM, FAU, PSL, UPB, SNS, SSSA, ITU, BME, ENPC, and PSL on a variety of topics related to innovation. The EELISA Innovation Talks provided interesting insights into the respective innovation ecosystems as well as into the challenges and opportunities we face.

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Glossary - Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

EELISA Innovation Talks. EELISA Innovation Talks aim to raise the public awareness – and thus also the scientific awareness – for the knowledge generated in EELISA and are publicly visible events and fora for discussion in the real and digital world. The events shall thematise the use of technology and innovation for sustainable development and develop a strong brand of EELISA for a broader public. EELISA Innovation Talks are an event series set up by EELISA InnoCORE.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

R & I. Research and Innovation

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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 45 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a joint roadmap of research infrastructures (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project, being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

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WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2 General considerations

EELISA Innovation Talks pursue the ambitious goal to bring the knowledge generated in EELISA to the broader public while making EELISA a vibrant forum for innovation and Europe, and the world, a better place. In order to achieve this ambitious goal, we have taken the following steps: Firstly, we set up a monthly event series that secondly, gives the stage to our best EELISA researchers and innovators to discuss the possibilities, risks, and opportunities of technology and innovation for sustainable development. Thirdly, we created an easily recognizable EELISA Innovation Talks event banner that is used to promote EELISA Innovation Talks and is updated before each event. Fourthly, we created a general EELISA Innovation Talks event webpage,² where general information about the event series and an overview of the EELISA Innovation Talks held can be found. Fifthly, we created event webpages for each individual EELISA Innovation Talk where specific information about each event can be found. Sixthly, we used EELISA media channels for innovation for promoting EELISA Innovation Talks on the central EELISA media channels as well as on the EELISA partners' local media channels. Seventhly, EELISA Innovation Talks are both on-site and online events easily accessible to the whole EELISA European University and beyond – no matter if during the event via live stream on YouTube or after the event on the EELISA YouTube channel. Eighthly, EELISA Innovation Talks offered the live audience the possibility to pose their questions to the speakers either on-site or online via comments on YouTube or via other integrated tools such as “slido” that organizers were encouraged to offer to the online-connected audience. Ninthly, when organizing EELISA Innovation Talks each partner institution was free to choose from a variety of appealing formats such as panel discussions, live talks, live interviews, or any other interactive format that it saw fit the purpose of this event series. Tenthly, apart from this general framework, EELISA Innovation Talks were rotating between the cities of our partnership and it was within the responsibility of each EELISA partner institution to organize their specific EELISA Innovation Talks. This included the selection of an appealing topic and location, an adequate format, qualified speakers, moderators, and a film team, as well as the general organization and promotion of the event (supported by the EELISA Communication Office and EELISA media channels for innovation). And last but not least, in the second reporting period from December 2022 to May 2024 EELISA Innovation Talks were hosted by by UPM, ITU, ENPC, UPM, FAU, PSL, UPB, SNS, SSSA, ITU, BME, ENPC, and PSL on a variety of topics related to innovation and allowed for some insights into the respective innovation ecosystems as well as into the challenges and opportunities they respectively we are facing.

The following will be an overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (2) providing conclusions from events held with the number of live attendees and evaluation of media distribution (hit rates etc.). The concept of EELISA Innovation Talks and the way of their implementation were already elucidated in D7.6 and will not be repeated here (see D7.6 “Overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (1)” pp.11-13 for the concept of EELLISA Innovation Talks and pp. 14-17 for the implementation of the concept of EELISA Innovation Talks). The overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (1) can also be found in D7.6 (see pp. 17-28).

² Cf. <https://eelisa.eu/an-open-stage-for-the-best-eelisa-researchers-and-innovators/>.

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3 Overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (2)

EELISA Innovation Talks being a monthly event series launched in June 2022 (with a summer break in August of each year) were held five times in the first reporting period and thirteen times in the second reporting period so that every EELISA partner institution organized two EELISA Innovation Talks. After the first reporting period with EELISA Innovation Talks hosted by BME, FAU, UPB, SNS, and SSSA, the following EELISA partners hosted EELISA Innovation Talks during the second reporting period:

- EELISA Innovation Talk # 6 was hosted by UPM,
- EELISA Innovation Talk # 7 was hosted by ITU,
- EELISA Innovation Talk # 8 was hosted by ENPC,
- EELISA Innovation Talk # 9 was hosted by UPM,
- EELISA Innovation Talk # 10 was hosted by FAU,
- EELISA Innovation Talk # 11 was hosted by PSL,
- EELISA Innovation Talk # 12 was hosted by UPB,
- EELISA Innovation Talk # 13 was hosted by SNS,
- EELISA Innovation Talk # 14 was hosted by SSSA,
- EELISA Innovation Talk # 15 was hosted by ITU,
- EELISA Innovation Talk # 16 was hosted by BME,
- EELISA Innovation Talk # 17 was hosted by ENPC,
- EELISA Innovation Talk # 18 was hosted by PSL.

In the following, an overview of these EELISA Innovation Talks (2) will be given that provides conclusions from events held with the number of live attendees and evaluation of media distribution (hit rates etc.). Additionally, a final section provides a table summarizing on-site and online participation in all EELISA Innovation Talks that were organized during the EELISA InnoCORE project (i.e., during the first and the second reporting period).

3.1 EELISA Innovation Talk # 6 hosted by UPM

The sixth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by UPM on 30 November 2022 from 17:30 to 18:30 (CEST) at the Paraninfo de la Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Calle Ramiro de Maeztu, 7) in Madrid. The topic of this sixth EELISA Innovation Talk was “**EELISA Alumni paving the way towards successful innovation, inspiring future change-makers**”.

Organizers from UPM chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “The sixth EELISA Innovation Talk will take place during the 19 actúaupm start-ups award ceremony on 30 November! During the ceremony, UPM will award the 1st, 2nd and 3rd prize to its best start-ups, as well the prize to the best project developed by students and the award to the project with highest social impact. The ceremony will be an opportunity to know more about the most promising start-ups born in UPM and meet the entrepreneurs behind them.”

To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 1) have been created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 6 hosted by UPM: <https://eelisa.eu/events/innovation-talk-session6-eelisa-alumni-paving-the-way-towards-successful-innovation-inspiring-future-change-makers/>

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Figure 1: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 6 hosted by UPM

This 60-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured talks by Beatriz Cerrolaza, co-founder and CEO of Alise Devices and Business Developer Manager at Thermophoton, and Ramón Martínez, founder and CEO of Dentaltix. Attendance was possible on-site at UPM and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

The event began with a welcome and introduction by Prof. Guillermo Cisneros, Rector of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Prof. Claudio Feijoo, the Rector's Delegate for Entrepreneurship, and Prof. Juan Manuel Muñoz-Guijosa, Associate Vice-Rector for Innovation and Technology Transfer, before the floor was given to the first speaker of the evening: Beatriz Cerrolaza.

Cerrolaza is a telecommunications engineer, PhD in Advanced Materials, and serial entrepreneur. After 6 years working as a researcher in public research centers, she decided to refocus her career and become an entrepreneur. In 2012, together with other colleagues, she founded the start-up Alise Devices. She has also participated in setting-up MyPublicInbox and recently joined the UPM spin-off THERMOPHOTON. Cerrolaza spent the first few minutes of her presentation talking about the accomplishments she and her colleagues have experienced over the past few years. She also talked about failures that happened in her career and how she learned from them. It was clear that she never gave up on working hard for her dreams. She was lucky to have crossed paths with other companies that expanded her knowledge and wanted to create a better planet for future generations. Cerrolaza was intrigued by those ideas and gladly joined their team. Finally, she thanked UPM for giving her the opportunity to present her work and win the first prize at the 19 actúaupm start-up award ceremony.

The winner of the second prize and second speaker of the event was Ramón Martínez. He is an architect from UPM and holds an executive MBA by IE Business School. In 2010, Martínez participated in the 7th actúaupm competition with his project Dentared, a project that is still ongoing and making progress. Martínez is the founder and CEO of Dentaltix, a B2B e-commerce startup for dental clinics, the largest online dental warehouse in Europe with more than 45,000 dental products. He began his speech with a personal story about his journey into entrepreneurship. Martínez also mentioned the effects that CoVid-19 had on his work. He finally included two books in his presentation that have helped him become a successful

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entrepreneur: “The Lean Startup” by Eric Ries and “The Hard Thing About Hard Things – Building a Business When There Are No Easy Answers” by Ben Horowitz.

After the talks, Prof. Claudio Feijóo presented the audience with some statistics on entrepreneurship at UPM. He stated that the UPM entrepreneurship program guarantees for employability, resilience, economic Growth, high-quality jobs, social impact, talent attraction, and a stable ecosystem. In a conclusion, he thanked all the people working on the entrepreneurship program. Finally, Beatriz del Rincón, the actúaupm communication manager, presented the startup awards and the winners had one minute to present their innovation program and project.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 6, hosted by UPM, is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 43 views as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 6 hosted by UPM: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2RSRsoUFy7o&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYmyIcXw8i7aZ4&index=6>

There were 74 live participants, of which 70 were present on-site and 4 followed the event live on UPM’s YouTube channel. Unfortunately, the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel did not work due to technical problems. In sum, the event was much more frequented on-site than online.

3.2 EELISA Innovation Talk # 7 hosted by ITU

The seventh EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by ITU on 11 January 2023 from 14:00 to 15:00 (CEST) at the Suleyman Demirel Cultural Center (SDKM) at İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi (ITU), Ayazağa, İstanbul. The topic of this EELISA Innovation Talk was “**The Role of Venture Capital in the Innovation Process: Examples from Turkey and Eastern Europe**”.

Organizers from ITU chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “Venture Capital (VC) firms represent key stakeholders in the innovation ecosystem. By providing equity for technology driven entrepreneurial firms in the early stages, they fuel high speed growth and help building competitive advantage. The panel will not only address how VC firms scout, select and deal with technology driven startups, but also try to uncover the value-added activities following the post-investment process. In an increasingly globalized market for capital, the panel will furthermore debate the degree to which early-stage startup deals are context-bound. Additionally, panelists will discuss whether the degree of radical innovations made by startups matter in closing a deal with the VC firms as well as the factors, which influence early-stage valuations.”

To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 2) have been created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk #7 hosted by ITU: <https://eelisa.eu/events/innovation-talk-7-the-role-of-venture-capital-in-the-innovation-process-examples-from-turkey-and-eastern-europe/>

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Figure 2: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 7 hosted by ITU

This 75-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured a panel discussion with two VC investors – Basar Yenidunya from 212 VC and Firat Ozpinar from Diffusion Capital Partners (DCP) – and was moderated by Prof. Mehmet Ercek, Faculty Member of Management Engineering Dept. at ITU, Mentor & Training Coordinator at ITU Cekirdek (top university-based incubator in Eurasia) and Deputy Director at ITU GINOVA (Entrepreneurship and Innovation Center). Attendance was possible in-person at ITU and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

The talk began with an introduction by the moderator, Mehmet Ercek, who set the stage for the discussion on venture capital's impact on innovation. The panel consisted of two experts: Basar Yenidunya from 212 VC and Firat Ozpinar from Diffusion Capital Partners (DCP). Each speaker provided insights based on their respective backgrounds, and the session was structured around a series of questions posed by the moderator. Topics of the evening included questions like how venture capital contributes to the innovation process and what are the key elements for VC investors when looking at start-ups. The speakers emphasized that venture capital provides crucial funding that enables startups to develop innovative products and technologies. It offers financial support, strategic guidance, and access to a network of industry contacts, essential for scaling innovative solutions. For the question “What do you look for in startups”, it was stated that VC investors typically seek startups with a strong management team, a scalable business model, a significant market opportunity, and a unique value proposition. It was examined that having a clear vision and a solid execution plan is crucial for attracting VC investment. The moderator also asked about the strategies of VC investors. The speakers answered that venture capitalists often guide the strategic direction of startups by participating in board meetings, providing mentorship, and leveraging their industry expertise to help startups navigate challenges and capitalize on opportunities. But maintaining a balance to preserve the startup's original vision is also important.

The question of risks intrinsically connected with VC funding was answered with the thesis that risks include the loss of control over company decisions, pressure for rapid growth, and potential misalignment between the startup's long-term vision and the short-term goals of investors. Therefore, start-ups have to consider investment terms carefully and have to choose partners accordingly. As a future approach to venture capital and emerging trends surrounding

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it, the speakers stated that those trends include a focus on sustainable and impact-driven investments, the rise of venture capital in emerging markets, and growing interest in sectors like biotech, fintech, and artificial intelligence. They are an important factor when thinking about shaping the future landscape of innovation and venture capital.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 7, hosted by ITU, is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 159 views and five likes as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 7 hosted by ITU: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I7Rb6ZGmKac&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=7

There were 40 live participants, of which 35 were present on-site and 5 followed the event live on ITU's YouTube channel. Unfortunately, there were some technical problems with the live stream. In sum, the event had a significant live audience and generated far more views online after the event than during the event.

3.3 EELISA Innovation Talk # 8 hosted by ENPC

The eighth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by Écoles des Ponts ParisTech (ENPC) on 28 March 2023 from 08:00 to 09:30 (CEST) in Paris. The topic of this eighth EELISA Innovation Talk was **“Digital Twins: Will They Enable Europe to Move Towards Sustainable Infrastructures?”**.

Organizers from ENPC chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “The digitalisation process has completely changed the way we do things and introduced new processes. One of these processes is called digital twins. Although they were discovered a long time ago, digital twins did not attract worldwide attention until the beginning of the new millennium. By creating a digital representation of a physical process, this technology provides an overview and a better understanding of given processes. In this EELISA Innovation Talk, our speakers will delve deeper into the subject by discussing what exactly the concept of digital twins is, how we can apply this technology in new areas, and what role engineers can play in its application?”

To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 3) have been created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 8 hosted by ENPC: <https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talk-session8-digital-twins-will-they-enable-europe-to-move-towards-sustainable-infrastructures/>

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Figure 3: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 8 hosted by ENPC

This 90-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured a panel discussion with four distinguished speakers (Jeremy Bleyer, Guilhem Villemin, Baptiste Escoffier, and Vincent Lepetit) and was moderated by Sofia d’Aguiar, the Executive Director of EELISA European University, and the journalist Stephan Lemonsu. Attendance was possible on-site in Paris and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel. (Unfortunately, however, there was a general strike in Paris, which is why the audience was a lot smaller than expected.)

The introduction to the eighth EELISA Innovation Talk was given by Anthony Briant, the Director of Écoles des Ponts ParisTech. He briefly presented the topic of “Digital Twins” and thanked the invited experts and the moderators for their participation in the event. The EELISA Innovation Talk had the format of a panel discussion, in which the moderators asked questions and the four speakers had enough time to give their answers. In the following, the main aspects of the four speaker’s answers will be summarized without following the chronological order of the panel discussion. The central question was whether or not digital twins will enable Europe to move towards a more sustainable future? In that context, the concept of digital twins was defined and different use cases were discussed.

The first speaker was Jeremy Bleyer, the scientific director of the Master Program on Digital Twins and researcher at the Navier Laboratory at ENPC. Bleyer proposed a definition of digital twins, which are digital representations of objects (or systems in complex projects) that function as a visualization that is constantly linked to data that ensures a continuous exchange between the digital twin and the real object. One of the difficulties Bleyer encountered in his research was using more than one algorithm to extract the desired data from the system. He sees a lot of potential in the project, but also a risk because it involves a lot of effort that could lead to failure if the system is not fully utilized. It needs to be maintained in the future.

The second speaker was Guilhem Villemin, Chief Technical Officer at Altametris/SNCF Réseau. According to Villemin, a digital twin must contain many details. For him, linking the objects and functions together is the main part of digital twins. He emphasized that in the railroad industry, obstacle detection is very important, and digital twins can help detect them

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by measuring the ballast on the tracks. Concerning the future of digital twins, Villemin is convinced that more research is needed to explore the full capacity of digital twins.

The third speaker was Baptiste Escoffier, Deputy Chief Technology and Systems Officer at Sanef Group. He presented his projects on digital twins. In his work, he tries to optimize decisions with the help of digital twins. For Escoffier, it is crucial that the data used by digital twins is 100% reliable and this is one of the most important aspects of his research in this field. Consequently, the data used by digital twins must be dynamic and in constant motion. Escoffier pointed out that the development of digital twins is making significant progress and that they have become an important part of engineering.

Finally, Vincent Lepetit, a researcher at the Laboratoire Informatique Gaspard Monge (LIGM), IMAGINE research group at ENPC, gave an overview of his work. In the context of his definition of digital twins, Lepetit stated that digital twins are all about planning and monitoring. A challenge that nearly always occurs is the collection of data to fuel the system of digital twins. He also emphasized that data must be transformed in order to be useful. Concerning future approaches to digital twins, Lepetit stated that one needs to pay very close attention to the series of small steps that make up the data system of digital twins. The Innovation Talk ended with a Q&A session that was open to the audience.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 8, hosted by ENPC, is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 168 views and four likes as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 8 hosted by ENPC: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=w-X8OH8cmj0&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=8

There were 26 live participants, of which 10 were present on-site and 16 followed the event live on the EELISA YouTube channel. Unfortunately, there was a general strike in Paris, which is why the on-site audience was a lot smaller than expected. In sum, the event generated more views on YouTube after the event than during the event.

3.4 EELISA Innovation Talk # 9 hosted by UPM

The ninth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by UPM on 19 April 2023 from 18:30 to 19:30 (CEST) at the Escuela Técnica Superior de Edificación UPM, 6 Avenida de Juan de Herrera in Madrid. The topic of this EELISA Innovation Talk was “**Entrepreneurship and Innovation in a Globalized World**”.

Organizers from UPM chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “The next UPM EELISA Innovation Talk will take place during the award ceremony of ActúaUPM’s best ideas competition, on 19 April 2023! During the ceremony, attendants will have the opportunity to get to know a selection of the best ideas gathered via the competition ActúaUPM (20th edition). In the framework of the ceremony, as EELISA Innovation Talk, we will have the chance to meet and get to know more about the experience of two successful innovators.”

To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 4) have been created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 9 hosted by UPM: <https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talk-session-9-entrepreneurship-and-innovation-in-a-globalized-world/>

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Figure 4: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 9 hosted by UPM

This 90-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured talks by Blanca Travesí, co-founder of U4IMPACT, a platform connecting students and companies, and Julio Ceballos, a specialist in internationalization, market strategy and commercial negotiation. Attendance was possible in-person at UPM and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

The event began with a welcome and introduction by Prof. Guillermo Cisneros, Rector of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, and Prof. Claudio Feijóo, the Rector’s Delegate for Entrepreneurship and then went straight on to the first speaker, Blanca Travesí. Travesi is a biomedical engineer with expertise in intelligent data analysis. During her university years she was co-founder and secretary general of the international cooperation association Inakuwa to promote women’s education in Tanzania. The topic of her presentation was: “Building social start-ups – generating social value and profitability?”

Travesí began with her personal life and broke down her career, starting with the experience of founding “Inakuwa”, a “non-profit association that was born in 2017 with the purpose of bringing education to groups without access to it with young people as protagonists of change” in Tanzania. She then referred to a new project called “U4IMPACT” which describes itself as a platform that connects companies and organizations with university students to promote impact projects. It stands for interconnection, accessibility and technology. It improves the employability of young people, sustainable business development, and social innovation.

The second speaker, Julio Ceballos, gave a presentation on “Competing everywhere for everything with everybody”. Ceballos is a lawyer-economist who has developed his career in Finland, Germany, Austria, the United Kingdom and China. Since 2006 he has managed the business of leading consumer brands (Pikolin, Telepizza, Pronovias, Scabal, etc.) in China. As an independent consultant, he advises Western companies in their sourcing and wholesale businesses, market multiplication and implementation processes in the Asian market. Along with his professional activity, Ceballos is a lecturer and gives courses on the geopolitical ecosystem of China and workshops on how to do business with the Asian giant. Ceballos introduced the audience to the world of innovation and entrepreneurship from the perspective

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of globalization. He emphasized that countries and companies are always competing for the best and the brightest. Ceballos then divided the community of entrepreneurs and innovators into two simple groups: those who travel and those who don't. He also emphasized that the world is facing a talent shortage due to an aging population and educational mismatches. This means that the economies of the countries that are able to attract talent will win. According to Ceballos, there's also a digital nomadism, which means that employees now know that they can work remotely after the global pandemic. Companies are now more flexible about where their employees work. He also explained why innovation is the new global standard and gave a structure on how to attract talent.

The last 30 minutes of the event were dedicated to the awards ceremony of actúaupm's best ideas competition. The winners presented their projects in a few minutes and were congratulated.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 9, hosted by UPM, is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 131 views as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 6 hosted by UPM: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ngdaTTBngV0&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=9

There were 108 live participants, of which 100 were present on-site and 8 followed the event live on the EELISA YouTube channel. In sum, the event seems to have had more appeal as a live event than as an online event.

3.5 EELISA Innovation Talk # 10 hosted by FAU

The tenth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by FAU in cooperation with Siemens on 3 May 2023 from 17:30 to 19:00 (CEST) at ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator, Zollhof 7, in Nuremberg, Germany. The topic of this EELISA Innovation Talk was **"Female Innovation"**.

Organizers from FAU chose the following teaser for the event webpage: "EELISA, Siemens, and Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU) cordially invite you to this EELISA Innovation Talk on the topic of "Female Innovation". The talk will be an exchange with successful female innovators who will share their experiences and views about "Female Innovation" and provide motivation, tips, and tricks for career advancement. The event is intended to be easily accessible to everyone interested in the topic and aims to provide a lasting impulse for your personal development. When it comes to innovation, women have great contributions to make. However, in the real world of innovation, be it in STEM careers, startups, or venture capital, women are still in the minority and a great deal of innovation potential is lost as a result. Why is that? What can be done about it? And how can female innovators nevertheless be successful? In this EELISA Innovation Talk, we will shed light on these questions highlighting different perspectives from successful female innovators who will share their experiences and give insights into their career paths, innovation experience, and views on female innovation. The audience will have the opportunity to ask their questions to the speakers and after the panel discussion, we will also have time for networking and enjoying snacks and drinks that will be provided."

To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 5) have been created:

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- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk #10 hosted by FAU: <https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talk-10-female-innovation/>

Figure 5: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 10 hosted by FAU

This 90-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured three inspiring talks by three successful female founders and experts on the topic “Female Innovation” and a subsequent panel discussion. The invited speakers were Laura Engelhardt, Head of Technology and Innovation Strategy at Siemens Technology and co-founder at PureEdge, Dr. Isabel Schellinger, Forbes “30 under 30”, medical doctor and founder of Angiolutions, and Lisa Gradow, deputy president of the Bundesverband Deutsche Startups e.V., serial founder, and business angel. The event was moderated by Dr. Judit Klein, Head of Startup Incubation at ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator. Attendance was possible on-site at ZOLLHOF and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

The event began with a welcome and introduction by moderator Judit Klein and a welcoming speech by FAU President Joachim Hornegger, who emphasized the importance of innovation and diversity at FAU. After a brief introduction of the panelists and the agenda by Judit Klein, the floor was given to Lisa Gradow who held a presentation on “Breaking Barriers – Female Entrepreneurs Shaping the Future”.

Gradow started by showing how hard it is to think of three major companies that were founded by women (even with the help of ChatGPT). Her thesis was that women are innovative, but not as likely to become entrepreneurs. Gradow gave some background on her own career as a (serial) entrepreneur, angel investor, and vice president of the German Startup Association, and supported her thesis with the latest results of the Female Founders Monitor that was recently published by her association. She went on to present some positive trends and the six key findings of the Female Founders Monitor. Additionally, she recommended mentorship, funding, education, and networking events as initiatives through which universities could strengthen female innovation and female founders. Finally, Gradow presented her principles for founding a company, which were courage, trust, all-in, common sense, confidence, and ambition, and ended her presentation with a call to action: one should give one intro per month for another female founder.

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The next speaker was Laura Engelhardt from Siemens with a presentation on “Celebrating female innovation”. She shared her personal experience as a female innovator and talked about how she dealt with the cultural and general integration of different minorities in a corporate context, but never thought about herself being in a minority or being different. Engelhardt presented her perspective on the topic of female innovation as well as her various projects to help female innovators succeed and be heard. Finally, she claimed that innovation is made by people with diverse perspectives and skills who co-create.

The last speaker was Isabel Nahal Schelliner, who started with her personal background of becoming a doctor and graduating from the medical school of FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg. She explained how she had got the opportunity to do research at Stanford University and talked about her research project on kidney disease. She and her team made some groundbreaking discoveries, and she eventually co-founded the medical technology startup “Angiolutions”, which aims to stop life-threatening aneurysms. Schellinger wanted to motivate young female innovators to pursue their projects and shared many important tips and strategies for startup founders.

After the three presentations, the EELISA Innovation Talk continued with an inspiring and engaging panel discussion, where moderator Judit Klein asked the panelists many important and interesting questions. Finally, the online and onsite audience also had the opportunity to ask their questions to the speakers. The event concluded with networking over snacks and drinks with the panelists.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 10, hosted by FAU, is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 110 views as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 10 hosted by FAU: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nbc8TjP-58o>

There were 85 live participants, of which 55 were present on-site and 30 followed the event live on the EELISA YouTube channel. In sum, through the cooperation with Siemens it was one of the EELISA Innovation Talks with the largest live audience on-site as well as online.

3.6 EELISA Innovation Talk # 11 hosted by PSL

The eleventh EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by PSL on 20 June from 09:00 to 10:00 (CEST) at the Parisanté Campus in Paris. The topic of this EELISA Innovation Talk was “**Deeptech Entrepreneurship & Innovation**”.

Organizers from UPM chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “From the 19th to the 23rd of June the DeepTech forum is going to take place at Parisanté Campus. This is a groundbreaking event, organised by the students of a Specialised Masters in Deeptech Entrepreneurship & Innovation of Mines Paris PSL and dedicated to the scientific, technological and economic challenges of the French Deeptech ecosystem. Over 4 mornings, researchers, entrepreneurs, investors, R&D managers and other players in the ecosystem will discuss the latest advances in scientific research and how they can be exploited in the economic world. Organised in the form of a series of lectures by experts and round tables, the aim is to provide an overview of future breakthrough innovations in the service of major contemporary challenges: Health, Energy Transition and Transport, Cybersecurity. A final ½ day will be devoted to Financing Deeptech. In this context, Université PSL is hosting this Innovation Talk session dedicated to Energy & Transport, and all EELISA colleagues are invited to virtually attend the session!”

To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 6) have been created:

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- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 11 hosted by PSL: <https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talk-11-deeptech-entrepreneurship-innovation/>

Figure 6: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 11 hosted by PSL

This 90-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured a talk by Greg De Temmerman, an energy physicist who is scientific director of the Quadrature Climate Foundation, associate researcher at Mines Paris PSL, and former director of the think tank Zenon Research. Attendance was possible in-person at PSL and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

After a short introduction, Greg De Temmerman started his presentation with the title “Moving without burning – Energy transition in the transport sector”. He explained that the transport sector with 73% is a very big and important part of the global greenhouse emissions. The other sectors are agriculture, forestry, land use, waste, and industry. To avoid the emission from the transport sector which come from fossil fuels, De Temmerman emphasized that the world needs more electricity and electric cars and less combustion engines. To show the progress of energy efficiency over time, De Temmerman chose the railway engines as an example to illustrate this point. De Temmerman illustrated his arguments with various graphics and diagrams that documented the progress. He then went into a deeper analysis of batteries and metals. Batteries are more long-lasting and function better overall today in contrast to earlier years. Minerals used in electric cars today are copper, lithium, nickel, manganese, cobalt and graphite. De Temmerman had a progressive outlook on the topic and explained how various materials and substances could increase the energy efficiency of electric engines in the future. Problems that could arise, like high expenses, were illustrated in different diagrams. The talk ended with a 10-minute Q&A session, in which the audience asked De Temmerman various questions about his presentation and his projects.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 11, hosted by PSL, is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 84 views as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 11 hosted by PSL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SYHkouz2gXY&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=11

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There were 44 live participants, of which 40 were present on-site and 4 followed the event live on the EELISA YouTube channel. In sum, the event seems to have had more appeal as a live event than as an online event and generated much more views after the event than during the event.

3.7 EELISA Innovation Talk # 12 hosted by UPB

The twelfth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by UPB on 28 September 2023 from 13:00 to 14:00 (CEST) at the Biblioteca UPB, room 2.2, in Bucharest. The topic of this EELISA Innovation Talk was “**Unleashing the Potential: Navigating the Early Stage of Spinoff and Startup Business Development**”.

Organizers from UPB chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “In this engaging talk, we will take you on a journey through the pivotal early stages of transforming cutting-edge research from academia into thriving ventures. Delve into the intricacies of customer discovery, “Jobs to Be Done,” value creation, and the powerful NABC framework. Discover how successful spinoffs and startups identify and cater to customer needs, uncover the core problems they aim to solve, and create tangible value that resonates with the market. If you’re curious about the art of entrepreneurial innovation and its impact on the real world, this talk is a must-attend event for academics, aspiring entrepreneurs, scholars, students and anyone passionate about the dynamic interplay between academia and business.”

To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 7) have been created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 12 hosted by UPB: <https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talk-12-unleashing-the-potential-navigating-the-early-stage-of-spinoff-and-startup-business-development/>

Figure 7: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 12 hosted by UPB

This 60-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured a talk by Razvan Craciunescu, who is Associate Professor and Future Networks Lab Coordinator at UPB as well as a former startup owner in IoT and Serious Games. He has worked for different Romanian startups (including

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the first Romanian unicorn) and is currently mentor and investor for local startups. Additionally, he works on the development of UPB's spinoffs and as a consultant for corporations in the field of tech transfer and research valorization. His research areas are: 5G, IoT, and applications for future networks, with more than 50 papers published. He was also a researcher at Aalborg University and an invited professor at Rochester University. Attendance was possible in-person at UPB and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

Razvan Craciunescu began this EELISA Innovation Talk by stating the main question that he promised to answer in his talk: "How to develop a tech startup?" Having extensive experience in this field as a founder, employee of a startup that became a unicorn, investor, and university professor, Craciunescu chose to structure of his talk around the most important lessons for tech startup founders. One of these lessons concerns the question, when starting a tech company, what should you look at? To answer this question Craciunescu introduced the commercialization triangle and explained all of its major components which are the application, the market, the competition, human resources, development time & cost, and IP rights & regulation. He emphasized that founders really have to understand the user need and competing applications. Each application may have its own market, but what is absolutely essential, is that one has to do a lot of early prototyping which should be as cheap and efficient as possible. This lesson was convincingly illustrated with a movie sequence from "The Founder". Another important lesson was the analysis of the market where founders should not just analyze the size of the market, supply and demand, etc., but also the "jobs to be done", a concept that was strikingly explained in a short video. It is crucial to understand the jobs to be done by products to really understand the customer needs, to be able to improve the products, and to understand the competition. Nearly phenomenological observations of the behavior of customers or users are the method of choice to understand the jobs to be done. Craciunescu also differentiated various customer groups – enthusiasts and visionaries on the one hand and pragmatists, conservatives, and laggards on the other – which are divided by a chasm that has to be crossed if one wants to scale one's startup successfully. For the business analysis Craciunescu proposed a simple framework with four parameters that should be intergrated into the value proposition. The value proposition puts forward an important client or market need addressed by a unique approach with compelling benefits when compared to the competition. Finally, Craciunescu discussed the business model of Nespresso and defined the most important skills for innovators and entrepreneurs. For him, they need to be empathetic to really understand their customers needs and to be willing to test their prototypes to learn from their customers to be finally able to offer successful products and services. In the Q&A session Craciunescu also gave some advice on how you can cheaply build prototypes of software applications.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 12, hosted by UPB, is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 37 views and one like as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 12 hosted by UPB: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y1WiCY46Ciw>

There were 11 live participants, of which 7 were present on-site and 4 followed the event live on the EELISA YouTube channel. In sum, the event was quite interesting, but unfortunately attracted only a very small audience.

3.8 EELISA Innovation Talk # 13 hosted by SNS

The thirteenth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by SNS on 30 October 2023 from 16:00 to 17:15 (CEST) at the Scuola Normale Superiore, Piazza dei Cavalieri 7, in Pisa. The topic of

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this EELISA Innovation Talk was **“Quantum technology and the second quantum revolution, now!”**

Organizers from SNS chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “As part of EELISA “Innovation Talks”, Scuola Normale has organised panel discussion exploring the fascinating realm of quantum technology and the second quantum revolution. This event promises to offer a unique opportunity for those outside the field to gain a firsthand understanding of quantum science and technology, with a particular emphasis on practical applications in industries and on information processing. Professors Fabio Beltram (SNS), Carlo Sirtori (PSL), and Vittorio Giovannetti (SNS) will discuss what QST is, what we can expect, and its practical impact on our world today. Industry guest speakers from IBM Quantum and a Scuola Normale Superiore’s spin-off, Planckian, will also be presented as examples of the transfer of QST research into industrial innovation.”

To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 8) have been created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 13 hosted by SNS: <https://eelisa.eu/events/innovation-talk-session-13-quantum-technology-and-the-second-quantum-revolution-now/>

Figure 8: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 13 hosted by SNS

This 75-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured talks by Fabio Beltram, Professor of Condensed Matter Physics at SNS and Director of the Nanoscience Laboratory NEST at SNS, Carlo Sirtori, Professor of Physics at the École Normale Supérieure at PSL, Vittorio Giovannetti, Professor of Condensed Matter Physics at SNS and Scientific Advisor at Planckian, Federico Mattei, IBM Quantum Business Development EMEA, Michele Dallari, the CEO of Planckian, and Sébastien Jezouin, Chief of Experiments at Alice & Bob. Attendance was possible in-person at SNS and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

The EELISA Innovation Talk started with a short introduction by Fabio Beltram, who then presented the first topic of the day: “Quantum technology: What is it? What to expect from it?” Beltram answered these questions in his short presentation and illustrated his explanations

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with various animations. Thus, he set the stage for the subsequent talks.

The next speaker was Vittorio Giovanetti, who gave a presentation on “Quantum technology: a journey from theory to technology”. Giovanetti gave an overview of the history of quantum mechanics from its beginnings in the early 20th century to the birth of quantum computing in the 1980s. Giovanetti also presented various contemporary applications of quantum physics that would have been impossible without the early discoveries in this field. Then, Carlo Sirtori went on to present some aspects of “Quantum for industry”. He argued that new technological breakthroughs in industry and academia using quantum concepts and phenomena and the need to educate a new generation of quantum engineers are bringing industry and academia together. He discussed two paths that can lead to a connection between industry and academia: The first is that the established industry looks for quantum knowledge from universities and research centers and the second is that young entrepreneurs from universities create new industries and startups. Sirtori emphasized that quantum technologies are currently introducing new paradigms for realizing new business ideas and products like quantum processors for much faster calculations or new physical processes for energy storage (like spin batteries). Finally, he described the three parts of the quantum tech market, namely computing, communication and sensing. The fourth speaker, Federico Mattei, presented his work on “IBM Quantum Computing”. He started with a short introduction about the essence of performance, which consists of scale (number of qubits), quality (circuit fidelity) and speed (circuit execution speed). He then presented his project “IBM Quantum”. It has over 500,000 registered users, more than 25 quantum systems on the IBM Cloud, more than 2,000 scientific and research papers, and more than 250 members of the IBM Quantum Network. There are also the IBM Quantum Computation Centers, which are centers with dedicated quantum systems aiming to advance industry-specific initiatives and regional quantum ecosystems. The fifth speaker was Michele Dallari, who spoke about his startup, Planckian, which is positioned at the intersection of energy and quantum science and is developing quantum batteries. These batteries exploit quantum properties to achieve superior performance. The goal is to push the boundaries of the second quantum revolution from current to new quantum technologies. Last but not least, Sébastien Jezouin gave a presentation about “Alice & Bob – Quantum computing with Schrödinger cat qubits”. Jezouin presented the startup “Alice & Bob” that was created in 2020 and has more than 15 patents filed, 30 million € of VC funding, 6 academic partnerships and a team consisting of approximately 70 people. The company has a big variety of experimental platforms, like spin qubits, photons, trapped ions and superconducting circuits. Its main focus is on ‘escaping decoherence’.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 13, hosted by SNS, is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 141 views and nine likes as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 13 hosted by SNS: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vYBtZk225_8&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=13

There were 42 live participants, of which 30 were present on-site and 12 followed the event live on the EELISA YouTube channel. In sum, the event seems to have had more appeal as a live event than as an online event and generated much more views after the event than during the event.

3.9 EELISA Innovation Talk # 14 hosted by SSSA

The fourteenth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by SSSA on 14 November 2023 from 15:00 to 16:00 (CET) at the Aula Magna of Scuola Sant’Anna, piazza Martiri della Libertà 33

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in Pisa. The topic of this EELISA Innovation Talk was **“Innovation & Sustainability: a challenging opportunity for the third Millennium”**.

Organizers from SSSA chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “This engaging talk explores the intersection of innovation and sustainability in the third millennium, emphasizing their critical roles in shaping our future. We will delve into how innovation can drive sustainability and vice versa, examining real-world examples and strategies for businesses, governments, and individuals to harness this synergy. Innovation is the catalyst for transformative change, driving breakthroughs in renewable energy, circular economies, and sustainable agriculture practices. It fosters eco-friendly technologies, smart cities, and resilient infrastructures, enabling us to reimagine transportation, healthcare, and education for a more sustainable world. However, innovation alone is insufficient; it must be paired with sustainability to protect our planet’s well-being. The journey toward innovation and sustainability presents complex and urgent challenges, requiring a paradigm shift, unwavering commitment to change, and a willingness to embrace unconventional solutions. It demands collaboration across borders, industries, and disciplines, urging us to think globally and act locally. We must rethink production and consumption, waste management, and the power of data and technology to create sustainable societies. Empowering communities, supporting green entrepreneurship, and investing in sustainable development are essential. Above all, fostering a culture of innovation and sustainability transcending political ideologies and economic interests is vital. The recognition of the interconnectedness of our actions is crucial, as strategies adopted ripple across ecosystems, economies, and societies. The path to innovation and sustainability requires shared decision-making. These challenges are opportunities to catalyze innovation, foster sustainability, and realize the UN 2030 Agenda, ensuring progress coexists with ecological balance and social equity. In today’s rapidly changing world, the intersection of innovation and sustainability presents a compelling and challenging opportunity. Innovation and sustainability are the twin pillars upon which the third millennium will be built. By embracing this challenge with determination and collective action, we can shape a sustainable future full of promise for generations to come. In conclusion, the talk highlights the compelling and challenging opportunity presented by the intersection of innovation and sustainability in the third millennium. It calls upon individuals, businesses, and governments to embrace this transformative journey toward a more sustainable future, one that holds promise for generations yet to come. By leveraging innovation and sustainability as twin pillars, we have the power to shape a brighter and more sustainable world for all. Join us as we discuss exciting prospects and the imperative for individuals, businesses, and governments to embrace this transformative journey towards a more sustainable future.”

To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 9) have been created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 14 hosted by SSSA: <https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talk-session-14-innovation-sustainability-a-challenging-opportunity-for-the-third-millennium/>

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Figure 9: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 14 hosted by SSSA

This 60-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured talks by Marco Frey, Full Professor of Economics and Business Management and Vice Rector for the Third Mission and Technology Transfer at SSSA, and Michele Barberio, Business Development Manager and ESG & Sustainability Consultant. Attendance was possible in-person at SSSA and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

The first speaker was Marco Frey who began his talk by introducing the basic principles of sustainability and the definition of the term. Furthermore, he discussed the challenges of sustainability and how difficult it is to maintain or create sustainability in the modern world. Frey then invited the audience to take a closer look at the history of sustainability and referred to several international attempts to make the world economy more sustainable. Additionally, he introduced five components of sustainable innovation that help solve the problems of sustainability: Sustainable innovation should be operational, collaborative, holistic, instrumental, and organizational. Frey went on to introduce two economic models for a sustainable future: the green economy and the circular economy. Finally, he examined the impact of sustainability in the contemporary world and how much progress was made in recent years.

The second speaker was Michele Barberio, who defended the thesis that nowadays sustainability is the “new normal” and the paradigm for economic transformation. He argued that humanity must face up to the environmental challenges and discussed some of the answers to these challenges, such as increasing resource efficiency in order to keep up with the demands of a growing population and drastically reducing carbon dioxide emissions. Barberio also presented some risks that could occur like the risk of non-compliance with public policies and regulations. He emphasized that relationships with stakeholders are the drivers of sustainable innovation (internal as well as external). An important factor in making relationships with stakeholders work is corporate culture. Barberio claimed that “sustainable innovations are likely to be more successful when they are deeply embedded in the firm’s culture”. Furthermore, he discussed some examples of the relationship between businesses and sustainability. The talk ended with a short Q&A session.

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The EELISA Innovation Talk # 14, hosted by SSSA, is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 97 views and one like as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 14 hosted by SSSA: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g6Mwv5k7oJg&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=14

There were 15 live participants, of which 10 were present on-site and 5 followed the event live on the EELISA YouTube channel. In sum, the event generated far more views on YouTube after the event than during the event.

3.10 EELISA Innovation Talk # 15 hosted by ITU

The fifteenth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by ITU on 13 December 2023 from 14:00 to 15:30 (CET) at the ITU Suleyman Demirel Cultural Center on the Ayazaga Campus in Istanbul. The topic of this EELISA Innovation Talk was “**Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Innovation: Implications and Challenges.**”

Organizers from ITU chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a hype and buzzword, traversing almost all scientific and technological domains. With the advent of generative AI many disciplines are expected to undergo radical change, or even, cease to exist. In this Innovation Talk, Assoc. Prof. Nazım Kemal Ure, Prof. Hatice Kose and Mert Menekse will discuss the classifications of AI algorithms, directions for future research and innovation in different domains as well as challenges posed by the dissemination of AI for certain industries and work. The panel will not only address experienced researchers in the field, but freshmen and other interested public to engage in a lively and interactive debate about the future of engineering and society.”

To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 10) have been created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 15 hosted by ITU: <https://eelisa.eu/events/innovation-talk-session-15-artificial-intelligence-ai-and-innovation-implications-and-challenges/>

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Figure 10: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 15 hosted by ITU

This 90-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured a panel discussion with Prof. Hatice Kose, Chair of the ITU Artificial Intelligence and Data Engineering Department and head of the Cognitive and Social Robotics Laboratory at ITU, and Mert Menekşe, co-founder of Co-One (a startup providing AI and crowdsourced solutions for data annotation, validation, and modeling). The event was moderated by Prof. Nazim Kemal Ure, Vice Director of the ITU Artificial Intelligence and Data Science Research Center and member of the ITU Artificial Intelligence and Data Engineering Department. Attendance was possible in-person at ITU and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

The EELISA Innovation Talk started with a welcome and introduction by Nazim Kemal Ure. The moderator emphasized that the talk was structured in such a way that both speakers should answer his questions. Ure’s first question simply was: “What is AI?” Kose argued that AI is basically the concept of transforming human thoughts into a technical system to increase its problem-solving efficiency. She said: “Don’t use it just because it’s fashion. Use it because you need it.” Mert Menekşe agreed and added that AI imitates human intelligence. From an economic point of view, AI is cheaper than human beings and can help to increase productivity. Ure also asked about recent discoveries and advances in AI, referencing academic papers that got the speakers excited. Kose answered that generative AI was the topic that most intrigued her and was most exciting in her research. She was fascinated by the way that AI can produce things by itself (also completely new things and ideas) and that it is sometimes scary. She also asked the question of how ethical the use of AI is and referred to more controversial aspects of Artificial Intelligence. Menekşe also drew inspiration from Marvel Comics, especially Tony Stark, also known as Ironman, who is extremely intelligent and invented an AI for his personal use named J.A.R.V.I.S. The panel discussion went on to discuss the controversial aspects of AI and the moderator also brought up the controversy of AI in music, where melodies, lyrics and everything else can be generated by AI to your liking. Many musicians have spoken out against this type of tool, saying that it takes away from the art of music and the work of real artists and musicians. But overall, this Innovation Talk focused more on the positive aspects of AI and explained a lot of them to the audience.

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The EELISA Innovation Talk # 15, hosted by ITU, is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 297 views and 15 likes as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 15 hosted by ITU: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o15HCWX1gUo>

There were 33 live participants, of which 20 were present on-site and 13 followed the event live on the EELISA YouTube channel. In sum, the event generated far more views on YouTube after the event than during the event.

3.11 EELISA Innovation Talk # 16 hosted by BME

The sixteenth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by BME on 7 February 2024 from 16:00 to 17:00 (CET) at BME. The topic of this EELISA Innovation Talk was “**Best practices from the Budapest University of Technology and Economics – BME**”.

Organizers from BME chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “Are you intrigued by entrepreneurship, intrapreneurship, spin-offs or start-ups? If you are curious about what those terms mean, and the entrepreneurial journey, this session is for you. Join us and gain inspiration from those who dare to reach for the sky while keeping their feet firmly grounded. During this online session, different BME experts will share their knowledge, pursuits and insights on innovation, go-to market strategies and more.”

To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 11) have been created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 16 hosted by BME: <https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talk-16-best-practices-from-the-budapest-university-of-technology-and-economics-bme/>

Figure 11: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 16 hosted by BME

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This 30-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured a panel discussion with Ádám Bárdos, CEO of iMotionDrive, one of BME’s pioneering spinoffs, Pál Koppa, professor and leader of the research project AHEAD, and Andor Réti, CEO of RESPRAY, a dynamic startup nurtured within BME’s ecosystem. The event was moderated by Gábor Dehelán, an innovation management expert at BME, and was planned as an online session. Unfortunately, however, due to technical problems it was not possible to access the live stream. There is no video of the event on the EELISA YouTube channel. Only an audio recording is available.

The panel discussed innovative pedagogical approaches adopted at BME. These include the integration of digital tools in the classroom, the use of virtual and augmented reality for immersive learning experiences, and the implementation of flipped classroom models. The talk also addressed the impact of these approaches on students and society. The thesis that students benefit from a holistic education that prepares them for the complexities of the modern workforce was put forward. Moreover, it was emphasized that the activities in the framework of EELISA have the potential to address pressing global issues, such as climate change and urbanization, through innovative engineering solutions. Looking ahead, there are a number of challenges that need to be addressed: These include ensuring equitable access to resources, maintaining the quality of education in the face of rapid technological change, and fostering a global perspective among students. BME and EELISA are committed to facing these challenges through continuous dialogue, research, and collaboration.

Due to technical problems, the EELISA Innovation Talk # 16, hosted by BME, is only available as an audio recording on the FIEK BME YouTube channel. It has 25 views and two likes as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 16 hosted by BME: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0IVoPh1r4RQ>

The event was planned as an online session, but due to technical problems, no access to the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel was possible.

3.12 EELISA Innovation Talk # 17 hosted by ENPC

The seventeenth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by Écoles des Ponts ParisTech (ENPC) on 20 March 2024 from 10:00 to 11:00 (CEST) at the Amphi Cauchy in Paris. The topic of this seventeenth EELISA Innovation Talk was “**2024 Olympic Games: Sport and Science Teamed Up**”.

Organizers from ENPC chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “Science and sport have long been closely linked. Scientific innovation has contributed to the development of athletic performance, to the creation of a better and fairer sporting environment, and to the creation of sustainable infrastructures for competitions. How can we optimize swimmers’ movements by using artificial intelligence and modeling? Can we predict the microbiological contamination of urban waters in order to use them for open water swimming? Is there a better format for football competitions?”

To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 12) have been created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 17 hosted by ENPC: <https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talk-17-2024-olympic-games-sport-and-science-teamed-up/>

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Figure 12: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 17 hosted by ENPC

This 60-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured presentations by four researchers from ENPC (Rémi Carmigniani, Brigitte Vinçon-Leite, Arthur Guillot-Le Goff, and Julien Guyon). Attendance was possible on-site at Amphi Cauchy, Écoles des Ponts ParisTech and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

The first speaker was Rémi Carmigniani, researcher at Laboratoire d'Hydraulique Saint-Venant (LHSV), Écoles des Ponts ParisTech. He started with the classification of different Olympic sports and chose competitive swimming as his main field of research. The topic of his presentation was: "Sport Physics – Olympic Swimming Start". The main aspects of the presentation include the study of coordination, propulsion & energetics, tracking & pacing strategies, and water resistance & drafting. By comparing different tactics in competitive swimming, Carmigniani wanted to research how the athletes can make the most of their strategies within the first 15 meters of the race. For comparison he selected three of the most successful athletes in competitive swimming, Caeleb Dressel, Florent Manaudou and Aleksander Popov and collected their data in a graphic for examination. Another question he asked was "How to maintain this initial high velocity as long as possible?" as the focus of the studies was also on the velocity of the athletes. With further looks at different tactics, Carmigniani created a guide for athletes with technical approaches to increase the efficiency of their swimming styles.

Next was Brigitte Vinçon-Leite, researcher at Laboratoire Eau, Environnement et Systèmes Urbains (LEESU), Écoles des Ponts ParisTech together with Arthur Guillot-Le Goff, PhD student at LEESU and LHSV laboratories, Écoles des Ponts ParisTech. Carmigniani was also part of the presentation, as all of the speaker's areas of interest were interrelated. Their topic was: "Legacy of Paris 2024 Olympic Games: Open water swimming in urban rivers". It started with a short overview of the sport and highlighted the conditions of climate change and heat waves and their effect on open water swimming. To continue the sport without difficulties, sanitation works in the Great Paris Region have been done. Vinçon-Leite also discussed the detection of fecal indicator bacteria in water and methods to test and detect them more quickly than before. Another question asked was, "How to prevent microbiological exposure?" To this end, Vinçon-Leite and her colleague Cuillot-Le Goff use the upstream detection point of the

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water and follow it to the downstream bathing area. There, they can analyze whether the bathing threshold has been exceeded and, if so, for how long. The study site was *Le bassin de la Villette* in the northern region of Paris, which is a place where a lot of sport events take place and also where numerous swimming basins are located. Other rivers studied include the Seine and the Marne. To estimate the transfer time of the contamination, a hydrodynamic model was created, distinguishing between meteorological forcing (air temperature, wind, rain, etc.), output (flow rate) and input (water level, water temperature, etc.).

Last but not least, Julien Guyon, researcher at the Centre d’Enseignement et de Recherche en Mathématiques et Calcul Scientifique (CERMICS) at Écoles des Ponts ParisTech, presented his research on the topic of football, namely “World Cup Draw: Quantifying (Un)fairness and (Im)balance”. He began his presentation with an insight from his personal experience when he was in Brazil in 2013, where everyone was preparing for the 2014 World Cup. He was particularly interested in the group stage, as he did not like the concept of it being very uneven. His initial idea was to structure the groups with a weak, a mediocre and a strong team to create balance. But due to FIFA rules, this was not possible, especially because two teams of the same continent cannot play in the same group. Guyon then constructed the system of drawing from four pots divided by the level of the teams. Very strong teams were found in Pot 1, while the weakest were found in Pot 4. To ensure that the FIFA rule (about two teams of the same continent not playing in one group) was not violated, he used mathematics, namely, a backtracking algorithm. Problems occurred when using groups of 3, namely schedule imbalance, loss of commercial and sporting attractiveness, teams playing a minimum of 2 matches and sporting integrity, as there is a high risk of collusion. The method of Guyon was adapted in the drawing for the World Cup in 2018.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 17, hosted by ENPC, is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 39 views and one like as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 17 hosted by ENPC: <https://youtu.be/mEN5inPxwok?si=Kt6rXLdx7xBngXmt>

There were 11 participants at the event, of which 5 were present on-site and 6 followed the event live on the EELISA YouTube channel. In sum, the event generated more views on YouTube after the event than during the event.

3.13 EELISA Innovation Talk # 18 hosted by PSL

The eighteenth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by PSL on 25 April 2024 from 18:00 to 19:00 pm (CEST) exclusively online via the EELISA YouTube Channel. The topic of this EELISA Innovation Talk was “**How can innovation support Corporate Social Responsibility?**”

Organizers from PSL chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “Can an alternative economic path address the challenges of sustainability? This question gains importance as societies worldwide deal with the imperative to integrate environmental and social considerations into the fabric of economic models. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) represents a paradigm shift in corporate philosophy, emphasizing ethical conduct, sustainability practices, and engagement with stakeholders. In this enticing conversation, speakers will spotlight and analyze the impact a synergy between CSR and innovation can have. Furthermore, this conversation will approach a better understanding of how the use of innovation can support and maximize Corporate Social Responsibility.”

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To promote the event, the following event webpage and event banner (Figure 13) have been created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 18 hosted by PSL: <https://eelisa.eu/events/innovation-talk-18-how-can-innovation-support-corporate-social-responsibility/>

Figure 13: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 18 hosted by PSL

This 60-minute EELISA Innovation Talk featured talks by Abdelkader Slifi, Associate Professor of Economy at Université Dauphine PSL, Camilo Muñoz Arenas, Graduate Assistant Professor in innovation and sustainability at UPM, and Martina Sáenz de Miera Espinosa, student entrepreneur at UPM and member of the EELISA executive committee and was moderated by Margaux Lamy who is a student entrepreneur at Dauphine PSL and founder of Horaé. Attendance was possible online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

The panel discussion was initiated by the moderator with the question about the definition of CSR and innovation. Abdelkader Slifi stated that the social responsibility of businesses originally was to increase their profits. This assumption was later critiqued by economists who emphasized that companies have to worry not only about their shareholders but also about stakeholders including among others workers, suppliers, and customers. With regard to innovation Camilo Muñoz Arenas stated that innovation is all about the proper understanding of which new inventions our society needs. Another question posed was about examples of CSR-driven innovations and all three speakers worked together to provide a variety of striking examples: These included a tech company using blockchain for supply chain transparency, a fashion brand developing eco-friendly materials, and a food manufacturer reducing waste through innovative packaging solutions. They demonstrated how businesses can address social and environmental challenges while achieving economic benefits. When it came to challenges and barriers of integrating innovation with CSR, different phenomena were discussed. Integrating innovation with CSR can face several challenges, including financial constraints, resistance to change, and a lack of knowledge or expertise. Companies may also struggle with aligning short-term business goals with long-term CSR objectives. Overcoming

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these barriers involves fostering collaboration across departments, investing in training and development, and creating partnerships with external stakeholders such as NGOs and academic institutions. The speakers emphasized that to ensure that CSR innovations are sustainable and scalable, companies should focus on creating solutions that are economically viable, environmentally friendly, and socially beneficial. Martina Sáenz de Miera Espinosa stated that companies should focus on these solutions and try to “create a highway” for CSR. This would involve rigorous testing and piloting of new ideas, engaging a wide range of stakeholders for feedback, and continuously iterating solutions to enhance their impact. Scalability can be achieved by designing innovations that can be adapted to different contexts and markets. Another important aspect of CSR is leadership. It plays a crucial role in fostering a culture of innovation and CSR. Leaders must prioritize CSR in their strategic goals and encourage a mindset of continuous improvement and experimentation within the organization. This involves setting clear CSR objectives, allocating resources for innovative projects, and recognizing and rewarding efforts that drive CSR through innovation.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 18, hosted by PSL, is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 74 views and three likes as of May 2024:

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 18 hosted by PSL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e3kLDxqM2zc&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=17

There were 12 participants at the event, which was exclusively online. In sum, the event generated more views on YouTube after the event than during the event.

4 Summary overview of on-site and online participation in all EELISA Innovation Talks (during the first and second reporting periods)

During the EELISA InnoCORE project, each EELISA partner institution organized two EELISA Innovation Talks, resulting in a total of 18 EELISA Innovation Talks. In total, these EELISA Innovation Talks were attended by 711 live participants and viewed by 2,745 people on YouTube. Let us now take a closer look at these numbers, beginning with the live participants and then continuing with the views, likes, and comments on YouTube. As a basis for this, we will use the following table (Table 2) that provides a summary overview of the on-site and online participation in all 18 EELISA Innovation Talks that were organized during the first and second reporting periods, i.e., between June 2022 and May 2024:

Number and Host of EELISA Innovation Talk	Live Participants on-site	Live participants online	Views on YouTube (as of May 2024)	Likes on YouTube (as of May 2024)	Comments on YouTube (as of May 2024)
Innovation Talk # 1 hosted by BME	20	15	167	1	0
Innovation Talk # 2 hosted by FAU	20	40	628	21	1
Innovation Talk # 3 hosted by UPB	52	8	242	8	1
Innovation Talk # 4 hosted by SNS	25	12	177	2	0

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Innovation Talk # 5 hosted by SSSA	10	12	125	3	0
Innovation Talk # 6 hosted by UPM	70	4*	43	0	0
Innovation Talk # 7 hosted by ITU	35	5	159	5	0
Innovation Talk # 8 hosted by ENPC	10	16	168	4	0
Innovation Talk # 9 hosted by UPM	100	8	131	0	0
Innovation Talk # 10 hosted by FAU	55	30	110	0	0
Innovation Talk # 11 hosted by PSL	40	4	84	0	0
Innovation Talk # 12 hosted by UPB	7	4	37	1	0
Innovation Talk # 13 hosted by SNS	30	12	141	9	0
Innovation Talk # 14 hosted by SSSA	10	5	97	1	0
Innovation Talk # 15 hosted by ITU	20	13	297	15	0
Innovation Talk # 16 hosted by BME	_*	_*	26	2	0
Innovation Talk # 17 hosted by ENPC	5	6	39	1	0
Innovation Talk # 18 hosted by PSL	_*	12	74	3	0

* Due to technical problems the livestream on the EELISA YouTube channel did not work. The four viewers were on the live stream on UPM's YouTube channel.

** Innovation Talk # 16, hosted by BME, was just online. No on-site participation was possible.

*** Due to technical problems the livestream on the EELISA YouTube channel did not work.

**** Innovation Talk # 18, hosted by PSL, was just online. No on-site participation was possible.

Table 2: Summary overview of on-site and online participation in all EELISA Innovation Talks (during the first and second reporting periods)

Of the 711 live participants attending all EELISA Innovation Talks, 509 were present on-site and 202 followed the events live on the EELISA YouTube channel. On average, each EELISA Innovation Talk was attended by 40 people, with the highest number of participants being 108 for EELISA Innovation Talk # 9, hosted by UPM, and the lowest number of participants being 0 (due to technical problems). Half of the EELISA Innovation Talks had at least about 40 live participants or more. The other half had less than 37 live participants. Taking only the 16 of

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18 EELISA Innovation Talks into account in which on-site participation was possible, EELISA Innovation Talks were attended on average by 32 on-site participants, again the highest number of 100 on-site participants being achieved by EELISA Innovation Talk # 9, hosted by UPM, and the lowest number being 5 on-site participants. In general, it seems to have been very difficult to attract an on-site live audience of more than 100 people to an English-speaking event format such as EELISA Innovation Talks. Taking only the 17 of 18 EELISA Innovation Talks into account, in which online participation was possible, EELISA Innovation Talks were attended on average by 12 online participants, the highest number of 40 online participants being achieved by EELISA Innovation Talk # 2, hosted by FAU, and the lowest number being around 5 online participants at 6 different EELISA Innovation Talks. As a live event on the EELISA YouTube channel with at least 30 online participants, EELISA Innovation Talks have only worked at FAU. The other EELISA Innovation Talks were only attended by very small online audiences of between 4 and 16 people. But this is only true for the live online audience. After the event, EELISA Innovation Talks were viewed by 2,745 people on YouTube. So let us also take a closer look at the number of views, likes and comments on YouTube generated until May 2024: All 18 EELISA Innovation Talks generated a total of 2,745 views, 76 likes, and 2 comments on YouTube. On average, each EELISA Innovation Talk generated about 153 views on YouTube. The most viewed video, with 628 views, was EELISA Innovation Talk # 2, hosted by FAU, and the least viewed video, has 26 views. In general, it seems to be very hard to generate more than 1,000 views and more than a dozen of likes and comments with a YouTube video with research and innovation related content such as provided by EELISA Innovation Talks. The only possibility to significantly increase these numbers, seems to be a more professional and entertaining content and significantly increased means put into marketing. In sum, EELISA Innovation Talks, with some variations, found their audience live and after the event, allowed for some interesting insights into our respective innovation ecosystems and the challenges we face, and succeeded in making our European University better known among our researchers and innovators.

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